

THE ROLE OF CREATIVE WRITING SKILLS IN ENHANCING CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS

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Abstract. *This article explores strategies to enhance narrative writing skills among higher education students, emphasizing its significance in fostering creativity, critical thinking, and effective communication. Narrative writing is a powerful tool across academic and professional domains, enabling students to articulate ideas compellingly and connect with diverse audiences. The article identifies common challenges students face, such as limited originality, structural issues, and language constraints, and proposes evidence-based approaches to address them. Key strategies include encouraging extensive reading, implementing regular writing exercises, and leveraging peer reviews and feedback. Additionally, the integration of technology, such as digital storytelling tools and online writing platforms, is discussed as a means to make narrative writing more engaging and accessible. By fostering a culture of storytelling through workshops, events, and interdisciplinary applications, the article highlights the transformative potential of narrative writing in higher education. The outcomes include improved analytical skills, creativity, and confidence, equipping students for academic and professional success.*

Keywords: *narrative writing, creative, writing proficiency, personal experiences.*

Narrative writing is more than just a creative endeavor; it is a fundamental skill that enhances communication, critical thinking, and the ability to engage audiences effectively. For higher education students, the ability to craft compelling narratives is vital, not only in humanities and social sciences but also in fields such as marketing, education, and even technical disciplines. Narratives help students express ideas, connect theoretical knowledge with practical applications, and share unique perspectives.

However, many students struggle with narrative writing due to challenges like insufficient creativity, poor structural coherence, and limited language proficiency. In a rapidly evolving academic and professional landscape, these limitations can hinder their ability to thrive. Thus, equipping students with robust narrative writing skills is a crucial part of higher education, empowering them to articulate their ideas clearly and compellingly. This article explores practical strategies to enhance narrative writing skills in higher education. It delves into the importance of fostering creativity, providing structured writing practice, and integrating modern technology into the writing process. By addressing the challenges and emphasizing the benefits of narrative writing, this discussion aims to offer educators and institutions actionable insights to support student development in this critical area.

Creative writing is one of the language skills required to be mastered by students in the educational institution considering that writing skill is an important indicator in language learning. In acquiring language skills, it is done usually through an integrated, chronological, and hierarchical process between one skill and another, namely learning to listen first, then speak, read, and lastly write (Astuti, 2014).

Writing is a way to put ideas or opinions into written form. It is a productive ability that holds significant importance realm of English language teaching and learning(Rafiq et al.,

2023). Writing is one of the essential English skills that is crucial across various educational fields, including language arts, social studies, science, and math (Isma, Hermansyah, et al., 2023; Isma, Rasmin, Hutauruk, et al., 2023)

Writing, as a productive skill that follows the development of receptive skills such as reading and listening, often remains a daunting challenge for many college students. This apprehension stems from the multifaceted demands of the writing process, which requires students to synthesize information, draw on personal experiences, interpret reading materials, and engage their creativity to produce coherent and compelling compositions. For many, these tasks can feel overwhelming, especially when coupled with the pressure to convey ideas clearly and effectively. Since writing is important to be taught, there are several types of text introduced in the first grade of senior high school, including Narrative text. According to Meer (2016), one of the four kinds of writing is narrative. Narrative text tells a chronological story from the past. Carroll et al. (2018) describe narrative text as a type of writing that tells a story by describing a series of events in a logical and chronological order, intended to engage readers by providing either real or imagined experiences.

A significant barrier to developing writing proficiency is the lack of confidence among students. This insecurity often hinders them from progressing beyond passive literacy activities, such as reading, to more active forms of engagement, like writing. As a result, their ability to express themselves through written language remains underdeveloped, limiting their potential to fully participate in academic discourse and creative exploration. Addressing these challenges is essential for fostering well-rounded literacy skills and empowering students to transition from consumers of information to confident creators of written content.

A significant barrier to developing writing proficiency is the lack of confidence among students. This insecurity often hinders them from progressing beyond passive literacy activities, such as reading, to more active forms of engagement, like writing. Research suggests that students' hesitancy to write is not merely due to a lack of skills but also due to fear of judgment and failure. When learners do not feel secure in their abilities, they tend to avoid risks, which stifles their creativity and prevents them from exploring complex ideas through written expression. Furthermore, Flower and Hayes's process model of writing highlights the importance of self-efficacy in composing texts, indicating that a student's belief in their ability directly influences their performance. Addressing these challenges requires creating a supportive environment that fosters confidence, encouraging students to view writing as a process of exploration and learning rather than a task subject to immediate evaluation. By shifting the focus from perfection to progress, educators can empower students to transition from consumers of information to confident creators of written content.

According to Bascon as quoted by Norton (1983:97) fairy tales are prose narratives which are regarded as fiction. They are not considered as dogma or history they may, or may not have happened and they are not taken seriously. Norton adds, "Because the tales are set in any time of any place, they are considered almost timeless and placeless." They usually tell the adventurous of animal or human characters. Fairy tales have no identified original author. They have been handed down from generation to generation by words of mouth.

Cumulative Tales are tales that build upon the actions, characters whether animals, vegetables, humans or inanimate objects, intelligence and reasoning ability. Cumulative tales can be found in the tales such as "Gingerbread Boy" and "The Fat Cat". Norton (1983:98)

Humorous Tales are folktales which allow people to laugh at themselves as well as the stupidity of the characters. The samples of Humorous Tales are the Russian tale “The Falcon under the Hat” and the English tales “Mr. And Mrs. Vinegar”. Norton (1983:98)

Beast Tales are folktales in which animals usually appear as characters that talk and act like humans. The tales of “The Billy Goat Gruff” and “The Little Red Hen” are the samples of this kind of fairy tale. Norton (1983:98).

Fairy tales, as described by Bascom and Norton, hold a unique position in literature as timeless and placeless narratives that transcend historical and cultural boundaries. These stories, often passed down orally through generations, serve not only as entertainment but also as a reflection of human creativity and imagination. Their fictional nature allows for the exploration of adventurous themes and characters, whether human or animal, providing valuable insights into the values, humor, and reasoning abilities of different cultures.

Various subgenres, such as Cumulative Tales, Humorous Tales, and Beast Tales, highlight the diversity within fairy tales. Cumulative Tales build incrementally on actions and characters, showcasing storytelling's rhythmic and repetitive qualities, as seen in stories like Gingerbread Boy and The Fat Cat. Humorous Tales bring levity and self-reflection, allowing audiences to laugh at the folly of characters, exemplified in The Falcon Under the Hat and Mr. and Mrs. Vinegar. Meanwhile, Beast Tales personify animals, endowing them with human traits, as in The Billy Goat Gruff and The Little Red Hen, to impart moral lessons or simply delight readers with imaginative scenarios.

Collectively, these tales continue to captivate audiences of all ages, offering both a connection to the past and a means to understand universal human experiences through the lens of fantasy and fiction. Their enduring appeal underscores their importance as a vital part of literary tradition and cultural heritage.

Creative writing serves as a powerful tool for honing academic writing skills, blending the freedom of expression with the discipline of structured thought. Through creative activities, students cultivate a unique voice, expand their vocabulary, and adopt innovative approaches to writing, enriching their academic work with greater depth. This practice sharpens their ability to organize thoughts, engage in critical analysis, and sustain a coherent narrative, enabling them to craft academic papers that are both articulate and engaging.

The advantages of incorporating creative writing into academic learning go far beyond the classroom, equipping students with versatile communication skills that are invaluable in various real-world situations.

Whether crafting persuasive arguments, composing analytical essays, or navigating professional settings, the blend of creativity and structure allows students to convey complex ideas with clarity and impact. Creative writing not only enhances technical proficiency but also instills a sense of enjoyment and engagement in the writing process, fostering confidence and adaptability in students as they develop into effective communicators.

By embracing the complementary nature of creative and academic writing, educators can guide students toward a well-rounded writing approach—one that balances expressive artistry with scholarly precision.

This integrated perspective equips students to excel academically and in broader contexts, empowering them to communicate ideas with both creativity and clarity.

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